

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CONDUCTIVE CFRP & GFRP USING PANI-BASED ELECTRICALLY CONDUCTIVE THERMOSET POLYMER MATRIX

V. Kumar¹, T. Yokozeki¹, T. Goto² and T. Takahashi²

¹Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, 113-8654, Japan
Email: vipin.kr27@aastr.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.u-tokyo.ac.jp>

²Department of Organic Device Engineering, Yamagata University
4-3-16, Jonan, Yonezawa, Yamagata, 992-8510, Japan
Email: t-goto@yz.yamagata-u.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.yamagata-u.ac.jp>

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, PANI-based electrically conductive thermoset matrix used to prepare conductive thermoset FRP composites. The conducting component of the matrix is polyaniline, protonated with a protonic acid, Dodecylbenzenesulphonic acid (DBSA). The thermoset matrix, for instance, Divinylbenzene (DVB) is used as a cross-linking polymer to enhance the rigidity. In this mixture, DBSA act as the dopant of PANI as well as the curing agent of DVB, this means that doping and curing of the composite occur simultaneously. More particularly, the present work reports the preparation of thermoset CFRP and GFRP composites which show very high electrical conductivity in thickness direction as well as good mechanical properties. Electrical properties, mechanical properties and morphology of these conductive FRPs have been studied and compared.

1 INTRODUCTION

The conductive composites have a great future scope in some of the practical applications. The change in electric and dielectric properties in the composite on application of load gives a promising area of research to fabricate more sophisticated as well as strong piezo sensors. Dielectric properties of conductive composite have also attracted the attention of researcher. The application of PANI-based composite in EMI shielding has already been established in the past and hence more progress in the current technologies will result into more reliable and accurate EMI shielding materials.

Since the discovery of the conductive polymers, there have been a tremendous research in this field. Researchers have studied variety of conductive polymers like, Polypyrrolle [1], Polypropylene [2], polyaniline [3] etc. However, polyaniline (PANI) has been studied most extensively among all intrinsic conducting polymers. Higher stability, low cost and controllable conductivity are some of the main advantages associated with the usage of PANI. However, poor solubility was one of the main issue with the PANI which was solved with the use of heavy protonic acid for the doping of PANI. PANI doped with heavy protonic acids have shown better miscibility and processibility. Different protonic acids as PANI dopant have been studied in past and their properties have been compared. HCL [4], CSA [5] and DBSA [5] are some of the most commonly used acids for PANI doping. However, due to the surfactant properties and solubility in most of the organic solvents, DBSA gained popularity over other protonic acids. Different doping phenomenon also have been studied and compared in past [6]. Haba et al. reported new PANI-DBSA/polymer blending technique via aqueous dispersion [7]. In past, the mixture of PANI-DBSA has been used as conductive fillers with different insulating polymers like polystyrene (PS), polyamides and epoxy resin to prepare conductive polymer composites [8,9]. The mechanical properties of PANI-based

composites with different reinforcements like CNT and natural rubber [10,11], also have been investigated by the researchers.

Variety of thermoplastic matrix have been investigated with PANI as a conductive filler, for example PANI-DBSA/PS, PANI-DBSA/PE and PANI-DBSA/Co-PA composites were prepared by melt processing and it has been shown that with the same ratio of PANI-DBSA to matrix polymer, the electrical conductivity varied with different polymer matrix [12]. PANI based thermoset composite also have been studied by the researchers. For example, Jia Q. M. et al. studied the electrically conductive epoxy resin composites containing PANI with different morphologies. They demonstrated that conductive composites containing PANI wires had the lowest percolation by comparison of that containing PANI particles or fibers. They also reported the maximum conductivity up to 10^{-4} S/cm for these composites [13]. Different electrically conductive FRPs composites also have been prepared using conventional fillers such as CNT or carbon black in the past and have been used for different purposes. For example, Vavouliotis A. et al. used electrical change method to determine the fatigue life prediction of the CFRP laminates. They used the MWCNT to prepare the conductive CFRP [14]. Similarly Song D.Y. et al. utilized the correlation between mechanical damage behavior and electrical resistance change in the CFRP composites as a health monitoring sensor. They conducted experiment and confirmed the results that the value of residual electrical resistance was dependent on the maximum strain applied [15].

The problems related to low conductivity value and complicated manufacturing process to prepare thermoset conductive composite have been tried to address in this present work. In most of the cases Epoxy with different conductive filler have been studied in past however, we have used DVB as cross-linking thermoset polymer to prepare the conductive matrix. In the present work, a simple single step technique to prepare PANI-DBSA/DVB conductive matrix has been used to prepare conductive thermoset FRPs.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Sample preparation

PANI-DBSA/DVB mixture has been prepared using technique mentioned in our previous work [16]. It was observed that, polymerization of DVB started immediately in case of centrifugally mixed PANI and DBSA. Therefore, the stability of the composite was very low at room temperature. The reason for early polymerization of DVB was the presence of extra free DBSA to initiate the polymerization of DVB which results into a fast polymerization. Higher the content of DBSA, faster the polymerization. Therefore to achieve the higher stability of the matrix at room temperature, roll-milled PANI-DBSA has been used in the present work. In this fine homogenous PANI-DBSA paste less amount of free DBSA was available to react with DVB and hence a more stable PANI-DBSA/DVB mixture was obtained. PANI to DBSA ratio in the roll milled samples has been kept at 30:70 by weight percentage which is equivalent to the molar ratio of 1:0.69 of PANI: DBSA. This ratio has been selected by considering the ideal ratio of 1:0.5 for PANI doping and the extra free DBSA for DVB polymerization. The rolled milled PANI-DBSA mixture with fixed ratio has been used with different weight percentage of DVB (30%, 50% and 70%) with corresponding weight percentage of PANI content (21%, 15% and 9%) and DBSA content (49%, 35% and 21%) respectively, to prepare 3 sets of PANI-DBSA/DVB mixtures. The mixture of PANI-DBSA/DVB was further used as matrix to impregnate the carbon fabric cloth and glass fabric cloth using hand lay-up process. The impregnated stacks of CFRP and GFRP were cured using Hot-press machine (Toyoseiki. Mini test press.10) for 2 hours at 120°C to prepare the final composites. 3 samples of each PANI-CFRP and PANI-GFRP have been prepared and Samples of different dimensions were cut for various measurements (electrical & mechanical properties). Three samples for electrical conductivity measurement and three samples for mechanical properties measurement have been used. Same samples have been used for morphological study. At higher DVB content, the viscosity of the solution becomes too low and therefore solution drain down through fabrics stitching, On the contrary, lower DVB content results into highly viscous blend which is very difficult to apply to the fabrics and also get cured in a short time, leaving a very small window of time to apply the matrix to the fabric cloths. Therefore, manufacturing parameters are very critical to obtain desired results of these composites.

2.2 Measurements

The electrical conductivity (DC measurement) of the samples were measured using a resistivity meter (3522-50 LCR HiTESTER, Hioki E.E. Corporation) by four probe method. DOTITE conductive adhesive paste (supplied by Fujikura Kasei Co. Ltd.) and aluminum tape have been used to measure the conductivity. DOTITE was applied and aluminum tape was attached to the perpendicular sides of the measuring direction of the sample i.e. thickness direction. DOTITE paste was dried completely before measuring the electrical conductivity.

The flexural modulus of the samples were measured using Universal Testing Machine (Instron-5582) by three-point bending method, using a load cell of the range of 5 kN and the crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The radii of loading nose and supports had been kept at 5 mm. The length, width and thickness of samples taken as 100 mm, 15 mm and 2.5 mm, respectively, while the span distance taken as 80 mm [17]. The morphology of the samples has been studied using the optical microscope (Eclipse L150, Nikon Corporation).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Electrical properties

The electrical conductivity of the PANI-CFRP composite samples and PANI-GFRP composite samples were measured and analyzed as a function of PANI content. The effect of PANI content on the electrical conductivity of the PANI-CFRP composite and PANI-GFRP composite has been shown in Figure 1. It can be clearly seen from the figure that the PANI-CFRP composite with 9 wt % of PANI exhibits a conductivity value of 0.80 S/cm, which is much higher than the conductivity reported in epoxy based conductive composites with different polyaniline morphology mentioned in the literature [13]. The value of conductivity of the conductive thermoset CFRP composites have been found to be higher than other thermoset conductive composites mentioned in literature [9,18]. It has been observed that with the same amount of PANI content, PANI-GFRP composites samples show low electrical conductivity as compared to PANI-CFRP composite samples. Conductive nature of carbon cloth and non-conductive behavior of glass clothes can be attributed for such results. These promising results widen the scope of conductive composites for super capacitor, sensors and EMI shielding applications.

Figure 1. Electrical conductivity of CFRP & GFRP of 1 mm thickness w.r.t PANI content

Figure 2. Electrical conductivity of CFRP with 1 mm and 2.5 mm thickness w.r.t PANI content

It is evident from the plot that with the increase of the wt% of PANI-DBSA in both the composites, there is significant increase in the electrical conductivity. The effect of the thickness on the conductivity also has been studied. CFRP samples with different thickness i.e. 2.5 mm and 1 mm have been prepared and their electrical conductivity was compared as shown in Figure 2. It can be seen from the plot that with 30% of DVB content there is not any significant change in the conductivity. On the other hand, with the increase in the DVB content the electrical conductivity reduced in the 2.5 mm thick sample as compared to 1 mm thick samples. The reason for such behavior could be the low viscosity of the PANI-DBSA/DVB mixture at higher content of DVB, and hence the solution might have drained down to the bottom of the 2.5 mm thick CFRP samples and creating a non-uniform distribution of the matrix in the samples. Therefore, it should be noted that the manufacturing process and controlled parameters like curing temperature and curing time are also very important factor to have consistent electrical conductivity results.

3.2 Mechanical Properties

The flexural properties of the composites have been determined using 3-point flexural testing. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the load-deflection curve for PANI-CFRP composite and PANI-GFRP composite, respectively. As it can be seen from the plots that both composite samples do not demonstrate brittle failure and fail more gradually as compared to epoxy based CFRP composites. The failure in both the cases is not catastrophic or brittle as is the case with epoxy based composites. The failure mainly occurs due to the delamination between the layers on the application of the load on composite.

It has also been observed from the Figure 5 that the PANI-CFRP composite with the composition of 30 wt % of DVB, shows a flexural modulus of 33.45 GPa which increases up to 43.06 GPa with the 50 wt % of DVB.

Similarly, PANI-GFRP composite with the composition of 30 wt % of DVB, shows a flexural modulus of 11.12 GPa which increases up to 14.50 GPa with the 50 wt % of DVB. The value of flexural modulus of the PANI-CFRP composite with 50 wt % of DVB is quite comparable to flexural modulus value of epoxy resin based CFRPs. As expected, the flexural modulus of PANI-GFRP composite is very low as compared to PANI-CFRP composite. These results show that a CFRP & GFRP can be made conductive with good mechanical properties, by using PANI-DBSA/DVB conductive thermoset mixture as a matrix. The

decrement in the flexural modulus with 70% DVB also confirms that due to the low viscosity of the mixture at high DVB content, the distribution of PANI-DBSA/DVB matrix is not uniform in the composite at higher concentration of DVB.

Figure 3. Load-deflection curve of PANI-CFRP composite with different wt % of DVB.

Figure 4. Load-deflection curve of PANI-GFRP composite with different wt % of DVB.

Figure 5. Flexural modulus of CFRP with 2.5 mm thickness & GFRP with 1.5 mm thickness w.r.t DVB content

3.3 Morphology of the composite samples

The surface and cross section of PANI-CFRP composite and PANI-GFRP composite have been studied using optical microscope. In Figure 6, the surfaces and the cross section (after failure) of PANI-CFRP composites with 30, 50 and 70 wt% of DVB content have been compared. For different DVB content, a great difference between the microstructures of the samples can be seen. At higher content of DVB, more homogenous surface can be obtained due to proper dispersion of PANI-DBSA mixture in DVB. On the other hand, a low concentration of DVB results into a poor dispersion and hence agglomeration of PANI-DBSA blend in composite can be seen clearly in the images. Figure 6 consist of two columns, first column shows the morphology of PANI-CFRP composite's surfaces with different DVB content and second column shows the PANI-CFRP composites cross section after failure after bending test. Images (I) and (II) in first column clearly identifies the PANI-DBSA and DVB phases in the composite samples.

It has been further observed that the surface properties of the composites improve significantly with the increase of DVB content in the composite. The electrical and mechanical properties can be well understood with the help of morphology. The agglomerates of conductive PANI-DBSA mixture account for the high conductivity at low DVB concentration while good dispersion and dense cross-linking network at high concentration of DVB account for the better mechanical properties. As can be seen from the figures that the phases between PANI-DBSA and DVB can be seen more clearly at low DVB concentration as compared to higher concentration of DVB. It can also be observed from the right column that the failure in PANI-CFRP with 30 wt% DVB and 50 wt% DVB is due to the crack formation in the matrix, while for PANI-CFRP with 70 wt% DVB, the failure occurred at the interface of matrix and carbon fabric. A more detailed study about the interface properties between matrix and fabric will be conducted in future.

PANI-CFRP surface

(I)

(II)

PANI-CFRP cross section

(I)

(II)

Figure 6. Optical microscope micrographs of PANI-CFRP composite surface and cross section with (I) 30 wt% of DVB content (II) 50 wt% of DVB content (III) 70 wt% of DVB content.

4 CONCLUSION

The present work reports the preparation of thermoset CFRP and GFRP composites which shows very high electrical conductivity in thickness direction as well as good mechanical properties. 3 CFRP & 3 GFRP samples of 2.5mm thickness with different PANI (9, 15 and 21 wt. %) and DVB (70, 50 and 30 wt. %) content have been prepared and their electrical & mechanical properties have been studied. It has been found that the CFRP with the 21 wt. % of PANI content shows electrical conductivity of 1.19 S/cm in the thickness direction and a flexural modulus of 33.44 GPa. This conductivity is much higher than the Epoxy based conductive composite mentioned in available literature. CFRP with 50 wt.% of DVB content shows flexural modulus of 43.058 GPa, which is quite similar to the flexural modulus of bi-direction epoxy resin based CFRP composites.

Similarly GFRP with the 21 wt.% of PANI content shows electrical conductivity of 0.09 S/cm in the thickness direction and a flexural modulus of 11.12 GPa. Significant improvement in the electrical conductivity of the samples is observed with the increase in PANI content. A slight decrement in the flexural modulus is observed in composites with 70 wt. % DVB as compared to the composites with 50 wt. % DVB, this behavior can be assigned to the low viscosity of the matrix at higher DVB concentration. Highly conductive thermoset FRP composite with good mechanical strength have been reported in this work. From the results, it can be inferred that the PANI-based conductive thermoset CFRP and GFRP of the desired electrical and mechanical properties can be prepared by altering the content of PANI, DBSA and DVB.

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